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Sustainable Stabilization of Puducherry Inland Clay using Lime and Quarry Dust: Geotechnical Properties and ANN-Based Predictive Modeling

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Abstract

Objectives: To investigate the effect of lime and quarry dust, both individually and in combination, on the geotechnical properties of Puducherry inland clay using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) modelling. **Methods:** Clay samples were treated individually with varying proportions of lime and QD (7%, 14%, 21%, and 28% by dry weight) as well as in combination to assess improvements in geotechnical behaviour. Laboratory tests, including Atterberg limits, Free Swell Index (FSI), compaction characteristics, direct shear test, and Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS), were conducted to evaluate changes in soil properties. To forecast the parameters of stabilized soil, the ANN Simulink model was simulated using a neural network fitting tool after training. **Findings:** The experimental findings showed that the plasticity index was reduced by 25% and 37% with lime and QD stabilization, respectively. Lime- and QD-stabilized clay reduced the optimum moisture content by 20% and 35%, while maximum dry density increased by 10% and 35%, respectively. Cohesion was reduced by 28% in both cases. Regarding UCS, lime-stabilized clay showed an increase up to 21% addition before declining, whereas QD-stabilized clay showed continuous strength gain. FSI decreased by 35% and 28% in lime- and QD-stabilized clay, respectively. The combination of both lime and QD showed superior performance due to synergistic effects. ANN modelling with statistical indicators (R^2 : 0.95–0.99, RMSE <30%, MAPE <20%) effectively predicted geotechnical properties with less than 25% error. **Novelty:** Utilizing QD provides a sustainable alternative to lime while improving the geotechnical performance of clay soil comparable to lime. Using QD as a stabilizer also helps in addressing environmental waste disposal issues.

Keywords: Stabilization; Artificial neural network; Lime; Quarry dust; Simulink model

1 Introduction

Soil stabilization has long been a critical aspect of geotechnical engineering, particularly in regions where natural soils exhibit poor strength, high compressibility, and significant volumetric instability. Puducherry inland clay is one such problematic soil that poses challenges for infrastructure development due to its low bearing capacity and high plasticity. Traditional stabilization techniques have primarily relied on lime, owing to its proven ability to improve soil strength and durability through cation exchange and pozzolanic reactions; however, the extensive use of lime raises sustainability concerns, including depletion of natural limestone reserves, increased cost, and significant CO₂ emissions during lime production. To address these issues, many researchers have investigated industrial by-products as supplementary stabilizers: Bhardwaj et al. studied molasses and waste foundry sand with lime and observed a limited reduction in cohesion but a significant increase in shear resistance⁽¹⁾; Phanikumar et al. used lime sludge, a paper industry by-product, with 10% cement and reported significant improvements⁽²⁾; Mahdi et al. used construction waste to stabilize clay soils and found improvements in bearing capacity, cohesion, and swelling reduction, with undrained shear strength increasing by 175% and compressibility decreasing by 31%⁽³⁾; Rizgar et al. showed that 15% waste glass powder was optimal for improving clayey soils⁽⁴⁾. In this context, quarry dust, an abundant by-product of stone crushing, is considered in this study as a stabilizer due to its particle size distribution and mineralogical composition, which improve gradation, reduce plasticity, and enhance soil strength, while also contributing to sustainable waste management and cost reduction. In parallel, artificial neural networks (ANNs), which simulate the functioning of biological neural systems, have shown great promise in predicting geotechnical properties by learning from data and capturing nonlinear soil–stabilizer interactions. Previous studies have demonstrated the superiority of ANN-based models over traditional methods in predicting unconfined compressive strength (UCS), optimum moisture content (OMC), and maximum dry density (MDD) across various stabilizers and curing conditions^(5–10). Despite this progress, little research has examined the combined effects of lime and quarry dust on Puducherry inland clay, whose unique mineralogical and Geotechnical properties warrant focused investigation. Therefore, this study evaluates the independent and combined influence of lime and quarry dust on the geotechnical characteristics of Puducherry inland clay—specifically consistency limits, UCS, and shear strength—across different curing periods, while also developing ANN-based predictive models to simulate soil response under varying stabilization conditions, thereby providing a reliable tool for forecasting geotechnical performance beyond experimental bounds.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

For the study, soil samples were collected from a depth of 1.5 to 5 meters in Sudhagar Nagar (Latitude: 11°92'48.10" N; Longitude: 79°79'91.0) in Reddiyarpalayam, Puducherry. The study area's location map is shown in Figure 1. As per IS 1892-1979, the Auger boring method was used to gather the samples from the chosen area. Samples were collected in sealed bags and then moved to the lab. After drying, the soil samples were ground up in the pulverising machine. To stop additional moisture loss, the dried samples were once more wrapped in the airtight bags. According to the IS 1498-1970 plasticity chart, the soil was categorised as high compressible silty clay. The plasticity curve for the sample that was taken is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1 gives the geotechnical characteristics of the Puducherry clay investigated in the research.

Table 1. Geotechnical Characteristics of Puducherry Inland Clay

Properties Tested	Result Values		Values as per IS Code		IS Codes
Natural Moisture Content (NMC) %	32		30 – 50%		IS 2720 (Part 2): 1973
Wet Density (kN/m ³)	15.1		14 - 18		IS: 2720 (Part 28) – 1974
Free Swell Index (FSI) %	100		50-100%		IS: 2720 (Part 40) – 1977
Direct Shear	C (kN/m²)	ø (Degree)	C (kN/m²)	ø (Degree)	IS: 2720 (Part 13) – 1986
	3.81	8°55'	0 - 20	0° - 10°	
Liquid Limit	84		50 – 100		IS: 2720
Plastic Limit	42		35 – 50		(Part 5) –
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) %	23.53		16 – 22		IS: 2720
Maximum Dry Density (MDD) kN/m ³	16.4		16 - 19		(Part 7) –
Grain Size Analysis (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	1985 IS: 2720 (Part 4) – 1985
	71.11	28.89	50 - 85	15 - 50	

Fig 1. Location Map of the Study Area

Fig 2. Plasticity Chart of Collected Sample

Lime used in this study collected from Thondamanatham in Villianoor District. Lime, due to its high alkalinity and reactivity with clay minerals, is an efficient soil stabilizer that reduces flexibility and swelling while increasing soil strength through cation exchange and pozzolanic reactions. However, insufficient lime or poor drying might limit its function, making the use of quarry dust a more sustainable and effective stabilization technique. Figure 3 represents grain size distribution curve for the lime used in this study. Table 2 gives the geotechnical properties of lime used in this study.

Fig 3. Grain Size Distribution Curve for Lime

Table 2. Geotechnical Characteristics of Lime

Properties Tested	Result Values		Values as per IS Code	
Natural Moisture Content (NMC) %	Nil		Nil	
Wet Density (kN/m ³)	9.4		9 - 13	
Free Swell Index (FSI) %	Nil		Nil	
Direct Shear	C (kN/m²)	φ (Degree)	C (kN/m²)	φ (Degree)
	2.01	25°91'	0 - 20	0° - 30°
Liquid Limit	Nil		Nil	
Plastic Limit	Nil		Nil	
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) %	26.92		18 - 28	
Maximum Dry Density (MDD) kN/m ³	15.85		15 - 18	

Quarry dust used in this study collected from Thiruvakkarai, Villupuram district, Tamil Nadu. It is a by-product generated during the mechanical crushing of rocks in quarries. It consists of fine, angular particles rich in silica and alumina. In soil stabilization, quarry dust acts as a filler, reduces voids, enhances compaction, and improves strength and durability. Figure 4 represents the grain size distribution curve for the quarry dust used in this study. Table 3 gives the geotechnical properties of quarry dust used in this study.

Fig 4. Grain Size Distribution Curve for Lime

Table 3. Geotechnical Characteristics of Quarry Dust

Properties Tested	Result Values		Values as per IS Code	
Natural Moisture Content (NMC) %	Nil		Nil	
Wet Density (kN/m ³)	18.9		16 - 19	
Free Swell Index (FSI) %	Nil		Nil	
Direct Shear	C (kN/m ²)	φ (Degree)	C (kN/m ²)	φ (Degree)
	4.36	26°33'	0 - 20	0° - 30°
Liquid Limit	Nil		Nil	
Plastic Limit	Nil		Nil	
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) %	11.36		8 - 12	
Maximum Dry Density (MDD) kN/m ³	21.27		17 - 22	

2.2 Mix ID Details for Stabilization

Table 4 shows various mix ID for the stabilization. CC represents clay collected from the site that needs to be stabilized. To stabilize the clay, lime and quarry dust has been added at the rate of 7%, 14%, 21% and 28% by the weight of clay respectively and cured for 0, 7, 14, 21, 28 and 56 days. Combination of lime and quarry dust is taken as 40% lime and 60% quarry dust.

2.3 Experimental Investigations

A number of laboratory experiments were carried out to assess the geotechnical qualities of Puducherry inland clay in line with the applicable IS regulations. The tests included consistency limits, swell potential, compaction characteristics, shear strength parameters, and compressive strength to provide a full picture of the soil’s behaviour before and after stabilisation.

2.3.1. Geotechnical Properties

Soil samples were sieved at 425 μm to measure the Liquid Limit (LL), Plastic Limit (PL), and Plasticity Index (PI). The liquid limit was determined using the Casagrande device, but the plastic limit was determined by rolling soil threads on a glass plate until they reached 3 mm diameter. The PI, which represents the range of plasticity, was computed using the difference between LL and PL. The swelling potential of the soil was determined by immersing oven-dried samples in distilled water and kerosene. The free swell index (FSI) was calculated by comparing the volume increase when placed in water vs kerosene. The Proctor compaction test was used to assess the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD). Soil samples

Table 4. Mix ID details for stabilization

Sl. No	Mix ID	Description
1.	CC	Puducherry Inland Clay
2.	CC+7%L	Puducherry Inland Clay + 7% of Lime by the weight of Clay
3.	CC+14%L	Puducherry Inland Clay + 14% of Lime by the weight of Clay
4.	CC+21%L	Puducherry Inland Clay + 21% of Lime by the weight of Clay
5.	CC+28%L	Puducherry Inland Clay + 28% of Lime by the weight of Clay
6.	CC+7%QD	Puducherry Inland Clay + 7% of QD by the weight of Clay
7.	CC+14% QD	Puducherry Inland Clay + 14% of QD by the weight of Clay
8.	CC+21% QD	Puducherry Inland Clay + 21% of QD by the weight of Clay
9.	CC+28% QD	Puducherry Inland Clay + 28% of QD by the weight of Clay
10.	CC+7%(L+QD)	Puducherry Inland Clay + 7% of (L+QD) by the weight of Clay
11.	CC+28%(L+QD)	Puducherry Inland Clay + 28% of (L+QD) by the weight of Clay

passed through a 4.75 mm screen were compacted in a conventional mould in three layers of 25 blows each, and bulk density was determined. Moisture content was determined using oven drying. Shear strength parameters, cohesion (c), and angle of internal friction (ϕ), in consolidated drained conditions. Soil specimens were compacted in the shear box and subjected to various normal stresses till failure. Cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 38 mm and a height of 76 mm were constructed and tested for axial loading at a strain rate of 0.5-2% per minute. The peak load at failure was utilised to compute the soil's UCS.

2.3.2. Modelling with Artificial Neural Network

To reduce the material cost and time, many researchers are considering the use of neural networking models to generate predictions. Based on the predictions we can derive few ideas to pursue, which ultimately save time and cost. Using ANN seven models were simulated to forecast Plasticity index (PI), Cohesion (c), Angle of Internal Friction (ϕ), Optimum Moisture Content (OMC), Maximum Dry Density (MDD), Free Swell Index (FSI) and unconfined compressive strength (UCS). To simulate model to forecast the above-mentioned geotechnical properties, datasets that included 120, 87, 34, 87, 132, 72 and 97 respectively. All these data were collected from the previous literatures which are relevant to the present study are tabulated in Table 5.

Collected data were normalized and utilized to simulate the ANN model. For efficient evaluation of the model's success, the dataset was split into three subsets: training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%). This division was based on common machine learning approaches for balancing model training and performance evaluation. Three distinct layers make up a neural network as a whole. The first layer is the input layer, and they are percentage of stabilizers added and curing period. The hidden layer owns 10 neurons and case-wise outputs are taken in the last layer. Using neural fitting (NF) tool, the above neural networks were trained repeatedly until the accuracy of the training regression, validation regression and overall data regression was close to 1.

Once the models trained properly error histogram and regression plot for geotechnical properties have been derived from the neural fitting tool. The NF tool will simulate the model to predict the above properties. The simulated models were used to predict the experimental results of our current work and check with the error percentage. Network architecture, error histogram and regression plot for the geotechnical properties are shown in figures 5 to 7.

Figure 8 shows scatter plot for the predicted and experimental values of the geotechnical properties. Based on the experimental and predicted results, the coefficient of correlation (R^2), Root mean squared error (RMSE), Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) have been calculated and tabulated in Table 6.

After training the neural network, Simulink model generated automatically from the neural fitting tool was saved and opened for further prediction. After opening the Simulink model, the trained neural fitting tool will appear which have input and output unit on the either side of the model. The experimental details of the present study have been given as input in the trained model to predict the geotechnical parameters. Correlation between the experimental and predicted values were compared and found the error percentage is below 25.

Table 5. Details of Collected Samples

Sl. No	Authors	No. of Samples	Sl. No	Authors	No. of Samples
Plasticity Index			Cohesion		
1.	P. Sivapullaiah (2000)	9	1.	Evangelos (2004)	46
2.	Evangelos (2004)	18	2.	A. Bhardwaj (2023)	7
3.	Hamid Gadouri (2017)	27	3.	Yixian Wang (2019)	16
4.	Umit Calik (2014)	12	4.	Mohammed (2010)	5
5.	Khelifa Harichane (2011)	18	5.	O.O. Ojuri (2022)	6
6.	Phanikumar (2020)	10	6.	Muzamir Hasan (2021)	7
7.	Muzamir Hasan (2021)	7		Total	87
8.	Beyene (2022)	19	Free Swell Index		
	Total	120	1.	P. Sivapullaiah (2000)	15
Angle of Internal friction			2.	Umit Calik (2014)	12
1.	A. Bhardwaj (2023)	7	3.	Shelema Amena (2021)	10
2.	Yixian Wang (2019)	16	4.	Phanikumar (2020)	10
3.	Mohammed (2010)	5	5.	V. Janani (2023)	6
4.	O.O. Ojuri (2022)	6	6.	Beyene (2022)	19
	Total	34		Total	72
Optimum Moisture Content			Maximum Dry Density		
1.	Umit Calik (2014)	12	1.	Evangelos (2004)	46
2.	Khelifa Harichane (2011)	18	2.	Umit Calik (2014)	12
3.	Shelema Amena (2021)	10	3.	Khelifa Harichane (2011)	18
4.	Phanikumar (2020)	10	4.	Shelema Amena (2021)	10
5.	V. Janani (2023)	6	5.	Phanikumar (2020)	10
6.	M. Perera (2022)	5	6.	V. Janani (2023)	6
7.	Muzamir Hasan (2021)	7	7.	M. Perera (2022)	5
8.	Beyene (2022)	19	8.	Muzamir Hasan (2021)	7
	Total	87	9.	Beyene (2022)	19
Unconfined Compressive Strength				Total	132
1.	Subhradeep Dhar (2018)	9	Unconfined Compressive Strength		
2.	Hamid Gadouri (2017)	21	6.	Phanikumar (2020)	10
3.	Umit Calik (2014)	12	7.	Mohammed (2010)	5
4.	Khelifa Harichane (2011)	18	8.	M. Perera (2022)	5
5.	Shelema Amena (2021)	10	9.	Muzamir Hasan (2021)	7
				Total	97

Table 6. Statistical Indicators

Sl No.	Geotechnical Properties	R ²	RMSE	MAPE
1.	Plasticity Index	0.98	17.86	9.18
2.	Cohesion	0.97	11.61	3.51
3.	Angle of Internal Friction	0.97	12.29	13.44
4.	Free Swell Index	0.95	12.96	16.75
5.	Optimum Moisture Content	0.96	19.86	14.17
6.	Maximum Dry Density	0.96	7.39	13.84
7.	Unconfined Compressive Strength	0.97	5.05	13.22

Fig 5. Network Architecture

Fig 6. Error Histogram

Fig 7. Regression Plot

Fig 8. Scatter Plot for the predicted and experimental values of Geotechnical Properties

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Geotechnical Properties

Figure 9(a) gives variations in the plasticity index of all mixes for the curing periods from 0 to 56 days. From the figure it is evident that untreated clay shows high PI value at zero curing days denoting its highly plastic nature. Addition of lime and quarry dust decreased the PI across all curing periods in a structured manner. Clay treated with lime showed reduction in the PI as the percentage of lime increased from 0 to 21% however the reduction in the PI is almost stopped at 28% and this may be due to saturation of cation exchange and pozzolanic reactions between the lime and clay minerals. In contrast, quarry dust treated clay showed a uniform reduction in the PI and this is due to granular nature of quarry dust as a non-plastic filler, which diluting

the clay fraction and reduced the plasticity. Combined lime and quarry dust treated clay outperformed than the individual treated clay. This performance observed in the combined treated clay with 28% at 56 days showed lowest PI, this enhancement attributed to the synergic effect of lime and quarry dust ie pozzolanic and filler effect. Overall, the results demonstrating that the combined effects of lime and quarry dust reduced PI in the most sustainable way compared to the individual treatment of clay along with curing periods. Sudhakar et al studied quarry dust treated clay, adding 25% QD for the treatment yield effective results and significantly reduced PI⁽¹¹⁾ considering the above findings combination of lime and quarry dust have been used up to 28% to stabilize the clay and the results obtained surpass the previous outcomes and yields better performance.

Figure 9(b) gives variations in the Free swell index of all mixes for the curing periods from 0 to 56 days. From the figure, it is evident that untreated clay shows high FSI value at zero curing days denoting its expansive nature. Addition of lime up to 21% there is a consistent reduction beyond which there is a slight increase in FSI values. This may be due to flocculation-agglomeration mechanisms where calcium ions replace monovalent cations reduce swelling potential of clay minerals. Quarry dust treated clay samples reduced the FSI with the increase in the quarry dust addition which is due to its filler effect that reduces the soil's swell shrink nature. Combination of lime and quarry dust also showed the most significant reduction in FSI, particularly at 28% addition at 56 days yielded the lowest FSI. This is attributed to the synergistic effect of pozzolanic reactions from lime and quarry dust improves the dimensional stability and minimizes swelling over time. Recent studies of Rathod et al, studied the combination of lime and quarry dust not only reduced swelling but also enhanced the durability under long term curing periods and it is due to the synergistic effect⁽¹²⁾ as similar to the present study.

Figure 9(c) & 9(d) shows the variations in OMC and MDD of all mixes for curing periods from 0 to 56 days. From the figure, it is evident that untreated clay exhibits a high OMC and a low MDD at zero curing days. The reduction in OMC with stabilization is attributed to cation exchange and flocculation caused by lime, while the increase in MDD is due to the inert, non-plastic, coarse nature and higher specific gravity of quarry dust. Many research findings showed that beyond 5% addition of lime leads to increased OMC and reduction in MDD however when it is combined with quarry dust up to 21% of lime addition give better performance in the present study.

Figure 9(e) & 9(f) shows the variations in Cohesion and Angle of internal friction of all mixes for curing periods from 0 to 56 days. From the figure, it is evident that cohesion values were systematically decreased while the addition of lime and quarry dust from 7% to 28% in contrast angle of shearing stress increased from 7% to 28% at all curing days. Combination of lime and quarry dust showed superior performance with 28% of lime and QD gives highest cohesion and angle of internal friction at the prolonged curing days of 56 days highlighting the synergistic effect of pozzolanic bonding property of lime and filler interlocking property of quarry dust. Kumar et al observed the similar results as we in this present study that lime contributed more to cohesion and quarry dust enhanced ϕ , and their combination produced the most effective stabilization across curing periods⁽¹³⁾.

Figure 9(g) shows the variations in Unconfined Compressive Strength of all mixes for curing periods from 0 to 56 days. Addition of lime up to 21%, UCS of treated clay show significant growth but beyond 21% it drastically dropped to zero. In contrast quarry dust treated clay increased the UCS value gradually up to 28%. Combination of lime and QD of 28% also increased the UCS value however it is less than clay treated with 28% of QD alone. With lime stabilization, the UCS increases significantly up to 21% lime content, reaching a peak value of 1300 kN/m² at 56 days curing. However, at 28% lime addition, the UCS drastically decreases across all curing periods, indicating strength loss due to excess free lime, which hampers pozzolanic reactions. On the other hand, quarry dust blends consistently show higher UCS values than lime-stabilized soils. The strength improvement with QD is progressive, reaching peak values of 1600 kN/m² for 28% QD at 56 days. Hybrid mixes (lime + QD) also performed well, though their UCS values were generally lower than pure QD mixes, suggesting quarry dust to be the dominant contributor to strength improvement. Phanikumar et al observed the similar observations that lime in combination with industrial byproducts improves early strength, but long-term gain depends on pozzolanic reactivity and filler effect of the additives. From the present results clay treated with quarry dust stabilization is more efficient than lime in enhancing the UCS of Puducherry inland clay⁽²⁾.

3.2 ANN Trained Model

The trained model was validated using the experimental test results obtained in this study. The input data for the simulation were derived from the experimental work, and the predicted outcomes were compared with the experimental results. The error percentage was found to be within 25%, demonstrating the reliability and accuracy of the simulated model. Figure 10 (a–g) presents the percentage error between the predicted and experimental values of the geotechnical properties for untreated clay, lime-stabilized clay, quarry dust-stabilized clay, and the combined lime–quarry dust stabilized clay at different curing periods of 7, 14, 21, 28, and 56 days.

Fig 9. Geotechnical Properties of Different Mix ID for Different curing Periods

The prediction error for the plasticity index is mostly within $\pm 15\%$. Minor fluctuations occur especially at higher lime contents which indicate that the model predicts PI reasonably well and consistent with the experimental stabilization results. The prediction error for cohesion and angle of internal friction lies mostly between $\pm 20\%$. Larger deviations are seen at the higher lime dosages which may be due to nonlinear pozzolanic reaction rate however predicted values follow the experimental pattern and angle of internal friction model also reliable to estimate the shear strength parameters. Moderate deviations observed in the FSI model lies between $\pm 20\%$. Free swell is more difficult to predict accurately because it is strongly influenced by clay mineralogy and microstructural changes, which vary with lime and QD stabilization. The prediction error percentage for OMC and MDD are $\pm 10\%$ and the deviations are small with minor fluctuations. The model predictions match well with experimental observations, as OMC and MDD largely depend on mix proportion rather than curing. The prediction error percentage for UCS

Fig 10. Variations in the Unconfined Compressive Strength of Different Mix ID for Different curing Periods

lies within $\pm 15\text{--}20\%$ for most of the mixes. The model tracks UCS development well across curing periods, demonstrating its reliability.

Previous research findings highlighted that combined stabilizers introduce complex chemical and physical interactions, leading to higher prediction uncertainties. The slightly larger deviations in FSI and Cohesion here are consistent with those reports. Very few researchers studied ANN based predictions of soil stabilization, errors of 15 – 25% were considered acceptable due to soil variability. The present study also falls within this acceptable range, validating the model’s reliability. The graphs confirm that the simulated model predictions are reliable, with most percentage errors within $\pm 20\%$, which is comparable to error ranges reported in similar stabilization and machine learning studies. Parameters such as MDD and OMC are predicted with higher accuracy, while FSI and Cohesion show slightly larger deviations due to complex physico-chemical interactions. M.S. Ouf et al found ANN–GA models accurately predicted UCS and FS% (>97% accuracy) for lime–GGBS stabilized soils,

enabling optimization of curing parameters and providing a transparent spreadsheet-based design tool this is also similar to the present study⁽¹⁴⁾. Heba Kumar et al. found that ANNs outperform conventional mathematical models in soil stabilization by nanomaterials, while in the present study MATLAB was employed for ANN training⁽¹⁵⁾. Khalid et al developed ANN models reliably predict UCS of stabilized soils, with most influential additives, validated statistically, offering a quick, accurate estimation method across variables⁽¹⁰⁾. Many researchers have used different method out of which taffels et al used ensemble method and found that this method outperformed than ANN model but in the present study ANN also performed in a better way⁽⁸⁾.

4 Conclusion

This study evaluated the stabilization potential of lime and quarry dust (QD), both individually and in combination, on the geotechnical behaviour of Puducherry inland clay, and employed Artificial Neural Network (ANN) modelling to predict the soil properties. Based on the experimental and simulated outcomes, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Inland clay soil stabilised with lime reduced plasticity and swelling potential up to 21% after that there is an increase due to excess free lime. Quarry dust outperformed lime, by reducing both parameters up to 28% addition of quarry dust. The combination of lime and QD reduced plasticity index than individual stabilisation which is due to the synergistic effects.
2. Lime-treated clay's unconfined compressive strength peaked at 21% addition, but QD-stabilized clay had higher UCS values that increased gradually up to 28%. Results from hybrid mixes were satisfactory, although the main source of strength augmentation was quarry dust.
3. While the angle of internal friction improved, cohesiveness decreased as the dosage of stabiliser rose. While quarry dust increased frictional resistance through granular filler action, lime primarily enhanced cohesiveness through pozzolanic bonding.
4. The ANN model trained in MATLAB Simulink was able to predict geotechnical parameters. High predictive capacity was demonstrated by the statistical indices (RMSE < 30%, MAPE < 20%, $R^2 = 0.95-0.99$). The prediction error for the present study was within $\pm 25\%$, which is similar to acceptable ranges documented in previous studies.

Overall, the findings confirm quarry dust as a sustainable and effective alternative to lime for clay stabilisation, either alone or in combination, with benefits in strength, density, and durability while addressing environmental and economic concerns. The use of ANN modelling improves the design process by delivering rapid, accurate forecasts, lowering experimental costs and promoting sustainable geotechnical practices.

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